

ORGANIZATION OF WRESTLING TRAINING IN SPORTS SCHOOLS FOR CHILDREN AND TEENAGERS

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Abstract: This article is intended for children and adolescents studying in sports schools is devoted to the development and practical justification of the forms, methods and means of organizing wrestling training.

Key words: SSCYT, teaching methods, method, tool, technique, attack, competition.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola bolalar-o'smirlar sport maktablaridagi kurash mashg'ulotlarini tashkil etishning shakl, usul va vositalari ishlab chiqish va amaliyotda asoslashga bag'ishlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: BO'SM, mashg'ulot uslublari, usul, vosita, texnika, xujum, musobaqa.

Annotatsiya: Dannaya statya prednaznachena dlya detey i podrostkov, obuchayushixsya v sportivnykh shkolax. posvyashchena razrabotke i prakticheskomu obosnovaniyu form, metodov i sredstv organizatsii trenirovki kurashistov.

Klyuchevye slova: DYUSSH, metody obucheniya, metod, instrument, priem, ataka, sorevnovanie.

Increasing the popularity of sports, clarifying the pedagogical conditions and didactic parameters of children and teenagers' interest in sports, and improving the pedagogical and psychological approaches to developing the physical qualities of young athletes in sports institutions are of particular importance in strengthening the health of the population in the world. Especially in the conditions of the pandemic, it becomes urgent to expand the pedagogical possibilities of developing the skills of students to follow an active movement regime, to develop individual physical development programs based on the criteria of the age, physiological and psychological development of the student based on the requirements of international and national competitions.

In recent years, in our republic, great attention has been paid to the development of children's sports, the introduction of traditional, innovative forms of strengthening and supporting the physical health of students at every stage of continuous education. In addition, it is important to improve the organizational and pedagogical foundations of wrestling training in sports schools for children and teenagers, to introduce innovative approaches to further increase the interest of students in wrestling training.

In our republic, J.M. Nurshin, R.S. Salamov, F.A. Kerimov, T.C. Usmonkhojaev, A.SH. Abdullaev, Sh.Kh. Forms and methods of enriching the educational content of physical education classes are highlighted in the studies of Khankeldiev F.A. Kerimov, N.M. Yusupov, SH.A, Abdullaev, R.D. Khalmukhamedov, V.N. Shin, G.B. Abdurasulova, S.C. Tajibaev, J.M. Nurshin, SH.A. Mirzaqulov, A.R. Taimuratov, N.A. Tastanov, Z.S. Artikov's scientific works reflect the history, organizational foundations and methodology of single combat sports. A. Atoev, J. Nurshin, R. Salomov, F. Kerimov, O. Toimurodov, J. Toshpolatov, H. Bobobekov, M. Sodikov, N. Azizov, Kh. Akhmedov development trends of wrestling sport, wrestling traditions , who developed the

scientific methodical bases of dependence on methods. They carried out scientific work on the history, organizational foundations and methodology of individual wrestling, the use of action games during training, and the development of physical qualities.

The organizational-pedagogical basis of organizing wrestling trainings in secondary schools showed the need for improvement. We tried to determine the level of students' achievement in wrestling using the following criteria: students' tactical and strategic preparation based on their physical training, individuality, leadership capabilities, levels of consciousness, evaluative attitudes, scope of objective understanding, expression of stable goals, interests and emotional and intellectual powers; they can understand the rules of fighting; know the rules of capture; interaction with the opponent; to attack; having the skills of self-defense and countermeasures; compliance with competition rules; to know the technique of belt wrestling; to be able to scientifically analyze movement techniques; level of physical fitness; general physical condition; special physical condition; achievements in sports.

For the experimental work of this research, which is aimed at studying the pedagogical conditions of wrestling training in secondary schools, it was carried out in secondary schools of Shovot district of Khorezm region, secondary school of Urganch city No. , in which a total of 13 coaches and 160 students participated. In order to carry out organizational-pedagogical activities in the period of experiments, using methods such as questionnaires, interviews, trainings, and question-and-answer methods, the informational-evaluative, practical and predictive levels of students in the struggle of secondary schools We will do a comparative analysis. Based on the results of the systematic analysis of the above comments, we analyzed the information-evaluative, practical and predictive levels of students in sports schools for children and teenagers (Table 1).

The results of mastering in determining the informative-evaluative, practical and predictive levels of children and teenagers in sports schools.

Table 1

Steps	groups	n	Appropriation degrees		
			good	Medium	small
informative - appraiser	experience	80	39	25	16
	control	80	28	27	24
Practical	experience	80	55	43	12
	control	80	25	31	24
Predictor	experience	80	60	13	7
	control	80	27	26	27

Based on the above results, the generalized, practical-theoretical-conceptual, practical-modeling and creative-analytical level of the continuous development of teachers' professional competence was mathematically and statistically analyzed, and from the obtained results it was shown that the criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of teaching is greater than one, and the criterion for evaluating the level of knowledge is greater than zero. can reach It is known that the mastery in the experimental class is higher than the mastery in the control class. It is worth noting that the results of the experimental tests conducted in children-adolescent sports schools to determine the level of effectiveness of the

informational-evaluative, practical and predictive levels of students' wrestling in sports schools are confirmed by statistical analysis. It turned out.

The researched scientific and pedagogical sources indicate that improving the organizational and pedagogical foundations of wrestling training in children's sports schools is becoming one of the priority goals of the educational process today. In this process, it was observed that insufficient attention was paid to the problem of learning and improving the techniques and tactics of training. : knowledge of the rules of capture, interaction with the opponent, ability to attack, self-defense and countermeasures, compliance with competition rules, knowledge of fighting techniques, scientific analysis of movement techniques level of physical training, level of general training, level of special training, achievements in sports. The interrelationship between these parts ensures that children and adolescents of sports schools achieve sustainable achievements in sports. As a result, athletes acquire intellectual and physical skills based on practical experience and theoretical knowledge.

In the process of pedagogical education, students' active assimilation of wrestling rules, concepts and information presented during the training, physical and tactical preparation, possession of their own fighting style as criteria for determining the level of preparation of students in wrestling training; it can be shown that there is a stable interest in learning the methods of struggle.

As a result of the experiments, each specific stage of wrestling training in children's sports schools has its own clearly defined goals, which promote the continuous development of students' tactical training from one regular stage to another. provides and improves. At the same time, a number of didactic conditions of a general nature are observed in improving the organizational and pedagogical foundations of wrestling training in youth sports schools. In particular, sportsmen's physical activities in children's and teenagers' sports schools, the rules of fighting as an important means of forming special training in them, the ability to interact with the opponent, attack, self-defense and implement countermeasures possessions, allows you to perform your actions consciously and thoughtfully.

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